

Operationalizing Theatrical Rhythm: Comparing Stopwatch-Based and Speech Recognition Methods for Measuring Speaking Rate

Rhythm is among the most *complex dimensions* (Morin, 1992) to grasp, particularly in the performing arts, where the intangible nature of performance resists formalization. Paradoxically, creative processes offer a fertile ground for observing rhythmic transformations, as the evolution of a production over time makes perceptible changes in prosody. This study compares two *operationalization strategies* (Moretti, 2014) aimed at tracking such transformations during rehearsals. Focusing on speaking rate as an indicator of rhythmic variation, we assess the affordances, limitations, and assumptions of two distinct yet complementary methodologies: one based on manual sequence timing, the other on automated speech recognition.

Across the course of a creative process in theater, we tend to specifically identify two main categories of transformations in actors' interpretations:

1. **Fluctuations** refer to actions that are reproduced identically but with variations in execution time.
2. **Mutations**, on the other hand, involve the emergence of new actions or significant modifications in the actors' gestures. Fluctuations influence the rhythmic quality of a performance (such as tempo, speed, or duration), while mutations affect its overall rhythmic structure (through additions, modifications, or removal of sequences).

This study aims to detect these transformations throughout the creative process by analyzing the evolution of speaking rate using two different methods, and to determine which of them is more effective at identifying whether these changes result from fluctuations or mutations.

State of the Art

Speaking rate analysis is well established in linguistics (Padeloup, 2004), information sciences (Rist, 1999), and cognitive sciences (Guiraud, 2017), or in interdisciplinary studies combining all

three (Pellegrino et al., 2011). However, methodologies differ significantly, particularly in their choice of measurement unit—ranging from syllables to words or breath groups per second. In theater studies, García Martínez's pioneering work (Martínez, 1995) laid foundational insights into the perception of rhythm by measuring the duration of breath groups, albeit on extremely limited samples. Building on recent digital humanities work, such as Bardiot's (Bardiot, 2021) and Escobar Varela's (Escobar Varela, 2021) calls to convert performance into analyzable data, this study aims to operationalize rhythm through the measurement of spoken words per second.

Corpus

Previous studies (Heugebaert, 2021) have shown that in Arthur Nauzyciel's creative processes, the duration and rhythmic structure of his productions evolve significantly due to transformations in performers' diction. By applying the manual stopwatch method to five Dress Rehearsal of *Les Paravents* and the automated speech recognition method to the rehearsals and early performances of *Le Malade Imaginaire* over 176 audio and video recordings of rehearsals, run-throughs and public performances spanning over two different productions of the play. To ensure data quality, recordings were filtered based on word recognition accuracy, and only those with a minimum accuracy threshold of 0.64 were included in the analysis. This resulted in a refined dataset from 13 runthroughs regrouping two representations from 2022, 3 Dress Rehearsals from 2023 and 8 of their following representations). We these two corpora, we are able not only to compare methodologies, but also to highlight the specific rhythmic dynamics of prosody in each creative context.

Methodologies

The first method is grounded in a "minimal computing" approach (Risam & Gil, 2022), using a stopwatch and pre-processed text files to calculate the speaking rate in Words Per Seconds (WPS). The observer segments the performance into dramaturgically meaningful sequences, and by correlating timed durations with word counts, determines average speaking rates. This method is particularly suited to real-time artistic contexts and fine-grained dramaturgical analysis but lacks precision inside of the sequences.

Figure 1. Speaking rate (WPS) curves from two Dress Rehearsals of *Les Paravents*, measured manually

The second method relies on automated speech recognition to extract time-coded data from rehearsal recordings. Using the open-source [vosk-model-fr-0.22](https://github.com/jdchart/dps) speech recognition tool, we extracted timestamps for each spoken word within the recordings. Once the starts and end times for individual words are identified, we parse them (<https://github.com/jdchart/dps>) into **time series graphs** representing speaking rate as Words Per Second (WPS), calculated using a rolling time window. These time series were then analyzed using clustering techniques (applied to the normalized time series) and curve comparisons, allowing us to distinguish between fluctuations (local variations) and mutations (structural shifts) across the rehearsal timeline.

Figure 2. Clusters of the Normalized Curves from WPS obtained by automatic speech recognition

Results and Discussion

Both approaches succeed in rendering visible the rhythmic transformations that occur during rehearsal. However, they illuminate different facets of the phenomenon. The manual DPS method offers immediate practical value for artistic teams and is well adapted to the live dynamics of the stage—but is limited to average values over predefined sequences. In contrast, the automated WPS method enables a diachronic, large-scale analysis of rhythmic evolution, yet is more vulnerable to the technical limitations posed by theatrical diction and recording quality. The study confirms that theatrical language, with its stylized intonation, non-standard prosody, and use of vocabulary outside pretrained models, presents specific challenges to computational analysis. Nonetheless, these limitations also reveal other dimensions of rhythm—such as sonic stylization—as critical sites of inquiry.

For example, in Figure (3), the highest peak—located at the 24-minute mark—indicates a variation in speaking rate greater than 0.7 and corresponds to the introduction of a microphone with heavy reverb effects. This significantly impacted the performance of the speech recognition system. Nevertheless, it remains possible to identify the emergence of a rhythmic mutation in the performance at this point; however, it is a **sonic** rather than **prosodic** rhythmic mutation.

In conclusion, drawing on two case studies from Nauzyciel’s directing practice, we show that operationalizing rhythm via speaking rate offers a means to render this elusive concept both intelligible and actionable as a compositional parameter. At the same time, this comparison underscores current methodological limitations, particularly in terms of speaker identification and data precision. Ultimately, this dialogue between approaches raises broader questions about the researcher’s role in data acquisition, the granularity of rhythmic metrics, and the place of digital tools in analyzing the temporality of live performance.

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